

ANALYSIS OF PROBLEMS RELATED TO STUDYING SPEECH ETIQUETTES IN ENGLISH

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Abstract. Today, in linguistics, much attention is paid to the difference between Uzbek and English etiquette. The comparative research method is becoming especially important. In this article, we will give general information about etiquette, and then we will look at English speech etiquette.

Keywords: culture, primitive period, people's outlook, human history, manners, speech etiquette.

АНАЛИЗ ПРОБЛЕМ, СВЯЗАННЫХ С ИЗУЧЕНИЕМ РЕЧЕВОГО ЭТИКЕТА НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. Сегодня в языкознании большое внимание уделяется разнице между узбекским и английским этикетом. Особое значение приобретает метод сравнительного исследования. В этой статье мы дадим общие сведения об этикете, а затем рассмотрим английский речевой этикет.

Ключевые слова: культура, первобытный период, народное мировоззрение, история человечества, нравы, речевой этикет.

Speech etiquette begins with compliance with the conditions of successful verbal communication: benevolent to the receiver, show interest in the conversation, "understanding" - adapt to the world of the internity, sincerely express one's opinion or empathetic attention. It determines the recipient's attention to the world of knowledge, expressing their thoughts in a clear form. The choice of the topic and the tone of the conversation is of the particular importance in the interlanguages, as well as emotional dialogues and free speech areas of communication. The factors that were mentioned play a special role in conducting the conversation.

Etiquette, as one of the most visible manifestations of moral culture, governs the external culture of a person, the observance of rules of behavior in mutual relations. In fact, the concept of "etiquette" appeared in ancient Egypt in 2.5 - 3 thousand years BC. The term etiquette was created at the end of the 17th century. However, ancient sources prove that the rules of etiquette in the form of customs, paintings and customs existed in the tribes since primitive times. Failure to fully comply with such rules was tantamount to betraying the community or tribe in which one lives. At first, such rules covered not only moral, but also legal, economic, religious and blood-kin relations. Every member of the team obeyed him unconditionally. In this way, etiquette did not have independent rules during this period, and was implemented mainly depending on the social problems of the community. In other words, these rules were created at the request of the natural community. The fulfillment of such requirements was supervised by the elders of the tribe or community. [2, 157]

Etiquette rules lead to manners, manners lead to politeness, politeness leads to morality. Therefore, morality is a set of positive actions that can be a model for society, time, and sometimes universally important for the history of mankind, as a spiritual phenomenon that determines the level of human maturity, important for the development of not only the

individual, but also the entire society. Therefore, etiquette can be called a new branch of linguistic science that serves to beautify the cultural and household lifestyle of a person of the technological age, culturalizing the system of mutual relations. [1, 263]

Speech etiquette refers to the linguistic signs and rules of their use accepted in this society at the moment in order to establish a speech connection between interlocutors and ensure communication in an emotionally positive tonality in accordance with the speech situation. For example, phrases in English speech etiquette: hi, how are you?, with my respect, let me introduce, it is an honour to introduce; welcome, here you are, bon appetite, with best wishes, bread and salt, tea and sugar, God supposes; thank you, help, please, let me express my deepest gratitude; stay healthy, see you, goodbye. [3, 36]

Speech etiquette is a universal language phenomenon that is characteristic of English languages. At the same time, each language has its own vocabulary of words and phrases that reflect the national specificity of politeness of speech. [4, 68]

Note the following units of speech etiquette found in the English language:

Greetings:

Nice to meet you

Invitation:

Would you like...?

Addressing:

Dear Sir or Madame

Excuse me

To make a request:

Can you do me a favour?

Sympathy:

Accept my condolences

Advices:

I would like to recommend you

When communicating with each other, people convey some special information or meaning, deliver something, ask for something, and perform certain speech acts. However, before entering the data exchange, voice communication must be entered, and this is done according to certain rules. We hardly notice them because they are familiar. The rules of speech etiquette are regulated by the rules of speech etiquette - a system of stable expressions developed in spoken language of English people and used in situations of establishing and maintaining communication. [5, 99]

Speech etiquette includes everything that expresses a friendly attitude to the interlocutor, creates a comfortable environment for communication. A rich set of language tools allows you to choose what is suitable for the speech situation and convenient for the addressee, you or you, the form of communication, setting a friendly, simple or, on the contrary, formal tone of conversation.

In general, by comparing some lexical semantic groups specific to speech etiquettes in Uzbek and English, and their comparative study, it will be of great importance to reflect the rules of etiquette and culture in these languages. Using good manners puts others before you and is a sign of respect and courtesy. Etiquette implies polite behavior and can help build relationships with people, whether it is applied in the workplace or at a social gathering. As some work

environments move towards more informal workspaces and open space, good manners become more important to building teamwork and positive communications amongst coworkers. Here are some tips to making conversations using good manners in English language: [6, 3]

- a) Make “please” and “thank you” part of your daily conversation;
- b) When someone says, “Thank you,” say “you’re welcome” in response;
- c) Avoid awkward words such as um, huh, hmm, nah and yeah. Instead, pause and think before speaking;
- d) Keep your tone of voice pleasant;
- e) Take care with “friendly put-downs” that actually tend to hurt and are not really funny like you intend, i.e. “shut up” or “so what”;
- f) Break the ice by asking questions such as, “Where are you from?” or “What are your hobbies?;
- g) Take turns talking and avoid telling long stories or sharing too many details;
- h) If you are on a cell phone in a public place, find a quiet place you can continue the conversation or keep your voice down so that the entire area does not have to hear your conversation;
- i) When leaving a message on an answering machine or voicemail, speak clearly; always indicate your name, who you are calling for and why you are calling;
- j) Be a good listener by nodding your head and making eye contact;
- k) Comment on what the other person has said;
- l) Do not interrupt while someone else is talking;
- m) Depending on the generation you are communicating with, consider not emailing, texting or talking on electronic devices while conversing with someone. For many, this is interpreted as disrespectful;
- n) Putting these tips into practice will enhance new conversations and strengthen relationships with friends and coworkers.

In general, until this day analysis of problems related to learning speech etiquettes in English has not been done enough yet. It is important to do some researches on this field of linguistics.

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